

DAFINET WORKSHOP

Pangasius and Tilapia production:

Upgrading Fish Health and Value Chains

University of Copenhagen, Frederiksberg Campus, Denmark

Program and abstracts

Dates: November 8th and 9th, 2016

Time: 10:00 to 17:00

Venue: Grand Lecture Theatre

Auditorium A1-1.01

Bülowsvej 17, DK-1870 Frederiksberg C, Denmark

Commercial Aquaculture in Bangladesh: Present Status, Constraints and Potentials

Seikh Razibul Islam

Department of Aquaculture, Patuakhali Science and Technology University, Bangladesh

Bangladesh is one of the world's leading fish producing countries with a total production of 3.68 million MT, where aquaculture production contributes about 56 percent of the total production. It is fortunate in having an extensive water resource in the form of ponds, natural depressions, lakes, canals, rivers and estuaries. Fisheries sector is contributing significantly in food security through providing safe and quality animal protein, almost 60 percent animal protein comes from fish. It contributes 3.69 percent to our national GDP and around one-fourth (23.12 percent) to the agricultural GDP. This sector has high potential for the perspective of economic development of the country. Over the last decade, dramatic increases in the production of a variety of species from commercial aquaculture systems and sharp increases in per capita fish consumption have occurred in Bangladesh. This transition has been made possible by widespread adoption of semi-intensive and intensive production practices. Pangas (*Pangasianodon hypophthalmus*) and tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*) are two commercially important fish species in Bangladesh. With the expansion of commercial aquaculture of these two species environmental degradation, outbreak of disease and production of quality fish have become the major issues. Low water quality in terms of pollution, lack of oxygen, toxic algae's, toxic substances and transfer of diseases etc. have numerous negative effects on production. The negative effects are identified as higher mortality, non-optimal growth rates, diseases and low quality of fish. Furthermore, low quality effects farm income through the price received, either locally or internationally, and is a barrier to export, because developing countries are facing progressively stricter food safety requirements, especially to the major markets in EU, USA or Japan. In addition to risk of diseases and accumulation of contaminants, the quality of the fish is challenged by off-flavor compounds in the pond water. All

together several environmental and man-impacted conditions threaten a future success for production of demandable freshwater fish in Bangladesh for both local and international markets.

Identifying Drivers of International Trade in Different Qualities using the Gravity Model: The Case of Pangasius Export of Vietnam

Afjal Hossain

Department of Food and Resource Economics

Faculty of Science, University of Copenhagen, Denmark and

Department of Economics and Sociology, Faculty of Business Administration and Management

Patuakhali Science and Technology University, Bangladesh

The gravity model is used to identify the drivers of international trade in different quality markets. The level of exports between Vietnam and different global quality markets is analyzed for identifying the specific driver(s) which influences the exports. We established the model for high, medium and low quality separately to find out the specific quality market to which the trade will be conducted and provides greater profits for the exporting country. Quality, an unobserved product characteristic, is difficult to measure but in this article we consider the high quality market to be 15% more than the average price per kg. of pangasius a year and 15% less for the low quality market. The middle quality market is in between. This paper compares the different quality markets in relation to the different drivers so that the exporter country and the single exporter company can detect the specific type of quality market for its followings trade giving emphasis on the particular driver(s) of international trade.